

EXAMINING THE EFFECT OF AGE AND GENDER ON ATTITUDES TOWARDS GENDER ROLES AMONG PAKISTANI ADULTS

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The purpose of this research was to examine the effect of age and gender on attitudes towards gender roles among Pakistani Adults.

Materials and Methods: In this cross-sectional study, 138 university students were purposively sampled. Gender role attitude scale was used to measure egalitarian and traditional gender roles among participants. Other demographic characteristics such as age, monthly house hold income and participant education were explored.

Results: Age significantly predicted attitudes of Pakistani adults towards gender roles. With increasing age, the individuals inclined towards egalitarian gender role attitudes. Significant gender differences were found among attitudes towards gender roles. Females had more inclination towards egalitarian role attitudes as compared to males, who favoured traditional gender role attitudes.

Conclusion: Understanding attitudes towards gender roles, whether traditional or egalitarian, is necessary because it can help us understand the latest trends in the social change and contribute to the development of interventions and policies to promote equality in the society.

Key Words: Age, Gender, Gender role attitudes

Introduction

Although feminism and women empowerment are prevailing across the globe, the women in southeast Asian countries are still battling against gender discrimination and struggling for their basic rights (Khalid, 2021). According to the Global Gender Gap Report 2025 by the World Economic Forum's (WEF), Pakistan stands second last in the global gender inequality index at 148th out of 148 countries. Only 36% of women in Pakistan take part in economic activities while the work force includes only 22.8 % of women. The WEF's also highlighted the gender wage gap in Pakistan, with women earning 18% less than men. The report further stated that gender inequality also existed at workplaces with 0.14

% of women at managerial positions as compared to 2.33% men. Only 25% of the Pakistani women with university level degrees are involved in the work force.

According to Farnon et al. (2021), gender discrimination is quite prevalent in Pakistan in homes, work places and educational institutes. This gender discrimination is perpetuated by stereotypical gender roles that is especially illustrated in the textbooks that are taught to children. Gender discrimination occurs when there is some sort of exclusion or restriction imposed on an individual on the basis of their sex, especially women (UNICEF,2017). Discrimination can be contained in both law or practice. For example, the discrimination due to law of a country can prevent a woman to

hold a job or leave the country without the consent of the husband, whereas discrimination due to practice may result in man a woman having a same job position and but having unequal wages or benefits (UNICEF,2017).

Since stereotyping gender roles leads to gender discrimination in the Pakistani society, the current study aims to assess the gender differences across the gender role attitudes and the relationship and the influence of age on the attitudes towards gender roles.

Gender stereotyping is defined as assigning certain attributes, characteristics and roles to people based on their gender. Gender stereotypes can be negative and benign. Gender stereotyping can be harmful when it limits a person's life choices, such as professional path, and life plans (UNICEF,2017)."

Literature Review

As stated by Khalid, (2021), Pakistan has a patriarchal society in which stereotypical gender roles, gender discrimination and gender inequality are deeply inculcated in the culture. UNICEF, (2017) defined gender roles as the social and behavioral norms that are commonly considered to be socially appropriate within a specific culture for individuals of a specific sex. The gender roles often impose the traditional responsibilities and tasks given to men, women, boys and girls.

Gender roles have two distinct categories traditional and egalitarian gender roles. As stated by Adil & Malik (2022), traditional gender roles talk about division of labor where women stay at home while men go out to work. Women are known to be homemakers while men are known to be the bread winners of the family. However, after industrialization, these traditional gender roles transitioned into egalitarian gender roles. Egalitarian gender roles postulated that women and men should be assigned responsibilities equally in all aspects of life (Adil et al., 2024).

Mursaleen (2024) assessed the gender role preferences and gender equality for different indoor and outdoor activities among middle class adults in Lahore. The gender role preferences were asked for different outdoor activities, such as shopping, visiting friends, playing sports, white collar jobs and high

caliber jobs as well as indoor activities such as taking care of the family, cooking, cleaning, washing clothes and cleaning washroom. The results revealed that in outdoor activities such as shopping, visiting friends and playing sports, gender equality was much higher, which indicated that the traditional views of woman staying at the homes had significantly changed. Similarly for white collar and high caliber jobs, the gender equality was present. The white collar and the high caliber jobs were considered acceptable for both men and women. However, in the case of indoor activities such as taking care of the family, cooking, cleaning, washing clothes and cleaning washroom, traditional views regarding gender roles were observed and a significant gender stereotyping was observed. Taking care of children, cooking and caring for siblings was flexible, but other domestic duties such as washing clothes and cleaning the washroom were attributed to women's work.

Khalid (2021) assessed the perception of gender equity among Pakistani adults ranging between 20-30 years who were undergraduates. She recommended to replicate her study with varied sample characteristics. Adil & Malik (2022) examined the magnitude of inclination of high school students towards egalitarian and traditional gender roles. The study discussed that the depiction of stereotypical gender roles is changing in Pakistan due to family, education and media. Therefore, this shift should be tested among both children who are receiving modern education. Adil et al. (2024) examined attitudes towards gender roles among government secondary school teachers. However, the sample had a limited generalizability.

Therefore, the study was conducted among both student and non-student population in order to increase its generalizability. The study was conducted among the current generation in order to examine whether the shift in the adoption of more egalitarian attitudes has actually occurred.

Theoretical framework

Social Learning theory

The social learning theory Bandura, (1977) explains that an individual can learn behaviors and associations not just by experiencing directly but also by observing, imitating and

modeling from others. For social learning to occur, the individual first pays attention to the model's behavior, remembers the behavior (retention) and then reproduces the observed behavior. Motivation is a key factor in imitating any behavior. An individual can be motivated to imitate a behavior if he receives an external reinforcement or punishment or observes the model being rewarded or punished.

In the case of gender roles, individuals since their childhood observe and learn from people around them such as parents, siblings, peers and media. They tend to observe, imitate and adopt the gender roles that are in accordance with the societal values. When they receive reinforcement for exhibiting those attitudes and behaviors, those behaviors, attitudes are further ingrained. For example, a child can observe his mother performing household duties and father going out to work and conclude that performing domestic work and working outside are appropriate gender roles for women and men respectively. Similarly, such gender roles can also be depicted through media. Ashraf et al. (2024) in their study revealed that Pakistani dramas played a significant role in shaping peoples' attitudes towards gender roles.

In this way social learning theory can explain how societal expectations, environment we live in and the content presented on media can shape us into developing traditional gender roles.

Objectives

1. To examine the relationship between age and attitudes towards gender roles among Pakistani adults.
2. To investigate gender differences between attitudes towards gender roles in Pakistani adults.

Hypotheses

1. Age will have a significant relationship with attitude towards gender roles among Pakistani adults.
2. There will be significant gender differences between attitudes towards gender roles in Pakistani adults

Methodology

Research Design and approach

For this study, a cross-sectional design was used with quantitative methodology.

Participant's selection and description:

The data was collected using purposive sampling technique from adult males and females in Rawalpindi and Islamabad. The age range of the sample of study was 19-32 years.

Data Collection and measurements:

Data was collected from participants using questionnaires. The researcher approached the males and females and verbally took their informed consent and also provided the written consent form. The participants were told about the purpose of the research. They were also ensured that the research has no possible risks since confidentiality and anonymity of their responses and personal information was maintained. They were also informed about the right to withdraw from the research at any point.

The informed consent form was given to the participants which explained the purpose of conducting this research. They were informed about the confidentiality of their provided information, voluntary participation and the right to exit research participation without experiencing any penalty. Researcher's email address was also given if the research participants wanted to ask any questions related to the study.

The demographic sheet comprised of information such as participant's age, education, and monthly house hold income. For assessing egalitarian and traditional gender roles, the gender role attitude scale was used. The gender role attitude scale Zeyneloğlu et al. (2011) is a 5-point Likert scale that consists of five subscales; Egalitarian gender roles, female gender roles, marriage gender roles, traditional gender roles and male gender roles.

For the current study, the items of egalitarian and traditional gender role subscale were utilized in order to compare egalitarian and traditional attitudes among individuals, as done by previous researches (Adil & Malik,2022).

The egalitarian and the traditional attitude subscales consisted of 8 items each. The

scoring of Egalitarian and traditional attitude sentences on Likert scale is: 5 points for 'completely agree,' 4 points for 'agree,' 3 points for 'undecided,' 2 points for 'disagree,' and 1 point for 'absolutely disagree.' Traditional attitude sentences have reverse scoring: 1 point for 'completely agree,' 2 points for 'agree,' 3 points for 'undecided,' 4 points for 'disagree,' and 5 points for 'absolutely disagree.' The scale scores range is 38 to 190. Higher scores indicate more egalitarian attitudes towards gender roles and the lower scores indicate more traditional ones.

The gender role attitude scale has a high reliability (0.92) and its subscales' have Cronbach alpha reliability coefficients ranging from 0.72 to 0.8 (Zeyneloğlu et al., 2011).

Data Analysis

Analysis of the research was carried out using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 26 (SPSS26). Demographic variables

were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The T-test was used to access gender differences and linear regression analysis was computed to test the relationship between age and attitude towards gender roles.

Ethical Considerations

For this research study, the following ethical guidelines were followed. Informed consent of the participants was taken before collecting the data. They were asked for their permission to participate in the study. They were also informed about possible benefits or risks of the research study and the right to withdraw from the research study at any point. The participants were also ensured that their responses were confidential and anonymous since no identity revealing information was asked. Therefore, the participation in this research won't pose any harm to the participant.

Results

Table 1 Frequencies and percentages for demographic variables. The table shows frequencies and percentages for age, socio-economic status and educational level of the participants.

Demographics	<i>f</i>	%
Gender		
Male	66	47.8
Female	72	52.2
Age		
18-24	96	69.6
25-32	42	30.4
Monthly house hold income		
Less than 55k	12	8.7
55k- 1.5lacs	120	87.0
More than 1.5 lacs	6	4.3
Education		

Currently in undergraduate	84	60.9
Completed undergraduate	18	13.0
Completed masters	24	17.4
Masters and above	12	8.7

Note: f=frequency, %=percentages

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics for egalitarian and traditional gender role attitudes subscales': The table displays the number of items in each subscale, their reliabilities, mean, standard deviation, actual and potential range, skewness and kurtosis values.

Sub Scale	No. of items	α	M (SD)	Range		Skewness	Kurtosis
				Potential	Actual		
Egalitarian attitudes	8	0.87	31.8(6.0)	16-40	1-40	-0.81	0.20
Traditional attitudes	8	0.70	22.5(4.7)	14-29	1-40	-0.01	-1.23

Note. M= Mean, SD= standard deviation

Table 3 Independent samples t-test for gender differences. The table shows mean, standard deviation and level of significance for gender differences in attitudes towards gender roles among adults.

Variable	Males		Females		t (138)	P	d
	M	SD	M	SD			
GRAS	52.6	7.4	55.9	7.8	-2.6	.01	0.43

Note. M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation, GRAS= Gender Role Attitude Scale, p=significance, d=Cohens d

T-test in the table 3 found significant gender differences among attitudes towards gender roles. The mean score for females was higher as compared to males which indicated that males were inclined to traditional gender role attitudes while females had a higher inclination

towards egalitarian gender roles. The effect size was found to be 0.43 which indicates a moderate difference between the attitudes of men and women towards the gender role attitudes.

Table 4 Pearson Correlation for age and attitude towards gender roles (N=138)

Variable	Age	GRAS
Age	-	.47**
GRAS	.47**	-

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$, GRAS= Gender Role Attitude Scale

As displayed in table 4, there is a significant positive correlation between age and attitudes towards gender roles.

Table 5 Linear Regression Results of Age and GRAS. The table displays the level of significance between age of the participants and attitude towards gender roles among participants.

Variable	B	SEB	β	T	p	95%CI	
						Upper bound	Lower bound
GRAS	1.05	.17	.47	6.16	.00	0.72	1.39
F	37.9						
R ²	.22						
ΔR^2	.21						

Note. N=138, B= Unstandardized Beta, CI= Confidence Interval, SE B= Standard Error for Beta, β = Standardized Beta Coefficient, t= Test Statistic, R² = Coefficient of Determination, ΔR^2 = Adjusted R², GRAS= Gender Role Attitude Scale

As presented in the table 5, linear regression found a significant positive relationship between age and attitude towards gender roles. The positive beta coefficient value depicts a positive relationship between age and attitude towards gender roles. This meant that as age increased, individuals adopted more egalitarian attitudes towards gender roles.

Discussion

The current study found a significant relationship between age and attitude towards gender roles. It also revealed a significant gender difference in attitudes towards gender roles. Moreover, in the table 2, the reliability analysis was also computed for the two subscales (traditional and egalitarian gender roles) from the gender role attitude scale (GRAS) which were used in our study. The Cronbach alpha reliabilities of both subscales are above 0.7 which is considered as a good reliability (field,2013). The skewness and kurtosis of both the scales also lie between the acceptable ranges of +2 and -2 (field,2013).

In our study, males had lower scores on the gender role attitude scale whereas the females scored comparatively higher. This indicated that the males were more inclined towards traditional gender roles whereas females were inclined towards egalitarian gender roles. Our results are similar to the study by Adil & Malik (2022) assessed gender attitudes towards egalitarian and traditional gender roles of high school students and also found that girls had

significantly stronger attitudes towards egalitarian gender roles as compared to men. Similarly, Adil et al. (2024) examined attitudes towards gender roles among Pakistani government high school secondary teachers in Lahore. The study found that female teachers exhibited an egalitarian attitude toward gender roles while male teachers exhibited a traditional gender roles attitude. Therefore, our hypothesis: "There will be significant gender differences between attitudes towards gender roles in Pakistani adults has been proved."

Since traditional gender role attitudes can also contribute to gender stereotypes, gender discrimination and gender inequity, the results of our study can also be compared to the study conducted by Khalid (2021). She assessed the perception of gender equity among Pakistani adults. The results indicated that men had significantly higher gender inequity scores than females.

Similarly, age of the participants was found to have significant relationship with the attitudes towards gender roles. Therefore, our hypothesis: "Age will have a significant relationship with attitude towards gender roles among Pakistani adults" has been proved. However, our results contradict the study conducted by Khalid et al. (2021) who didn't find any significant relationship between the age of the participants and the gender role attitudes. Possible reasons could be the increasing awareness regarding gender disparities, the demographics and the small sample size, due to

which trends prevailing in a localized area were captured.

Our findings can also be supported and explained through the social learning theory. The gender differences in our study can be explained by the observational learning experiences of males and females. The male individuals in our study might have observed the male figures such as father, brother in their homes with traditional gender role attitudes and receiving reinforcement for adopting traditional attitudes. This led them to imitate and exhibit traditional views towards gender roles. On the other hand, the female individuals might have observed their mothers or sisters suffering due to the traditional views on gender roles imposed by the society, or they might have observed the women in their homes such as mother and sisters adopting egalitarian attitudes towards gender roles and receiving reinforcement, which led them to imitate and exhibit egalitarian gender roles.

The current study had some limitations. The sample only included educated population. Future researchers should conduct similar studies on vast or older populations to obtain the trend among these variables at different age levels. Moreover, future researchers can carry out similar studies in different settings such as work places to access differences in attitude towards gender roles. The sample size collected for this study was small and the study was cross-sectional in nature. Future studies should collect data from large sample across Pakistan including both rural and urban areas and conduct longitudinal studies over the impact of gender role attitudes. Influence of other variables on attitudes towards gender roles such as socio-economic status, education and marital status can also be examined. These all measures will improve the generalizability and significance of results.

Implications

The following study has given an insight into the prevailing trends regarding depiction of gender roles in our society. This can further help us identify the inequalities and biases prevailing in Pakistan resulting due to these depicted roles in many domains including education, employment and in our homes and what we can do to change their attitudes and

reduce biases in these domains. By understanding the factors behind the attitudes towards gender roles of the individuals, further policies and interventions can be developed that can promote gender equality, empower women and reduce gender discrimination in our society. Lastly, the following study will help us understand the social change in our society on a broader perspective.

Conclusion

Understanding attitudes towards gender roles, whether traditional or egalitarian, is necessary because it can help us understand the latest trends in the social change and contribute to the development of interventions and policies to promote equality in the society.

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Declaration

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